

Talk abstract “Biosecurity measures reducing hepatitis E virus in pig herds – findings of the OHEJP project BIOPIGEE”, presented at the conference 22. Fachtagung für Fleisch- und Geflügelfleischhygiene (online) on March 1st-2nd, 2022

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Measures reducing the occurrence of hepatitis E virus (HEV) in pig herds are crucial to mitigate the risk of human HEV infections [1]. Comparing expert opinions and the results of a systematic review, relevant areas were identified where scientific evidence is lacking on the efficacy of measures to reduce HEV in pig herds.

Hepatitis E virus (HEV) is a zoonotic pathogen, which usually causes no clinical disease in pigs. In humans, HEV causes hepatitis that can be asymptomatic or acute self-limiting. Chronic infections are possible in immunocompromised individuals. In the EU, food-borne transmission from pigs and wild boars is assumed to be the major route of infections in humans [2]. The project „Biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe” (BIOPIGEE) of the One Health European Joint Programme (<https://onehealthjep.eu/>) aims at establishing a protocol of biosecurity measures relevant for reducing the occurrence of *Salmonella* and HEV in the pig production chain that is harmonised across countries. The protocol will be based on the combination of the results from literature reviews, an expert panel and own studies. Below, results of a systematic review of biosecurity measures to reduce the occurrence of HEV in pigs are compared to results from expert interviews.

In BIOPIGEE, a biosecurity measure was defined as a measure aiming at reducing the occurrence of HEV/*Salmonella* among pigs of a farm that is applicable by the farmer without changing major parts of her/his business. The studies were restricted to measures of external and internal biosecurity and excluded measures increasing the pigs’ resistance against HEV/*Salmonella*. Biosecurity measures were classified into one of the following categories: cleaning and disinfection of the pig area; feed, water and bedding; humans; mixing of pigs; material and equipment; other animals; purchase of pigs or semen; vehicles. In a systematic review, biosecurity measures were identified from peer-reviewed scientific articles and odds ratios (OR) for HEV occurrence in pig herds applying these measures were extracted. Concurrently, an online survey among experts in BIOPIGEE partner countries was conducted. The experts were asked to rank the relevance of the categories and to assess the importance of single measures.

In the systematic review, 15 measures were identified that aimed at reducing HEV occurrence in 16 observations in four articles. Of these, 12 were found to be effective resulting in an OR for HEV occurrence <1. The five most effective measures were

- wearing farm specific clothes,
- a shower prior to entering farm premises,
- a sanitary ford at the entry to housing facilities,
- no contact between pigs and other farm animals, and
- a perimeter fence.

The most relevant biosecurity measures as rated by the experts were

- all-in/all-out management,
- dedicated injection syringes and needles for each group,
- sufficient downtime period after cleaning and disinfection,
- protecting feed and bedding from other animals, and
- cleaning and disinfection of transport vehicles.

However, experts were not asked about all measures found in the systematic review and not all measures assessed by the experts were identified during the systematic review. Cleaning and disinfection of the pig area and mixing of pigs were rated the most relevant categories by the experts, whereas other animals and humans were rated least important. In contrast, published research on the prevention of spread of HEV between and within pig farms focused more on external biosecurity. There were relatively more effective measures reported that involved humans, vehicles, other species and the introduction of pigs than measures of cleaning and disinfection or concerning mixing of pigs. Further studies on measures reducing the occurrence of HEV in pig herds should consider internal biosecurity and include measures of the categories feed, water and bedding and material and equipment.

In BIOPIGEE, the biosecurity measures assessed by the experts will be evaluated in an observational study including pig farms throughout Europe. The systematic review is going to be expanded in order to identify more potential biosecurity measures. These results will be combined in a catalogue of biosecurity measures reducing the occurrence of HEV in pig production and a system to benchmark these measures. The catalogue of biosecurity measure and the benchmark system will provide useful tools to develop (further) programs to mitigate the risk of HEV cases in humans in Europe.

References

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